

Importance of the communication of university teachers in Peru, in virtual education: Systematic review

Importancia de la comunicación de los docentes universitarios del Perú, en la educación virtual: Revisión sistemática

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Abstract

The article is framed in the category of systematic review, responds to the review, analysis, and bibliographic selection of existing articles of the last 10 years, linked to the importance of university teacher communication in virtual education. It aims to describe the importance of university teacher communication in the teaching-learning process within virtual educational practice. He belongs to the research line of pedagogical innovation, is descriptively and methodologically has followed the guidelines of the flow of systematic review of the scientific literature, making use of the prism method, review table of articles, table of abstracts, statistical graphs of the reviewed scientific literature, analysis of the results, discussion, and conclusions of the reviewed literature. The results of the 23 selected articles make visible the position of different writers regarding the communication of the university professor, virtual education, the link between both criteria and certain characteristics; the literature reflects a lack of articles that delimit the impact of the communicative strategies used in the virtual education process. However, relevant information was found regarding the importance of communication and communication skills of teachers in their educational practice and in the process of training future professionals.

Key words: communication, virtual education, university professor.

Resumen

El artículo se enmarca en la categoría de revisión sistemática, responde a la revisión, análisis y selección bibliográfica de artículos existentes de los últimos 10 años, vinculados con la importancia de la comunicación del docente universitario en la educación virtual. Tiene por objetivo describir la importancia de la comunicación del docente universitario en el proceso de enseñanza aprendizaje dentro de la práctica educativa virtual. Pertenece a la línea de investigación de innovación pedagógica, es descriptiva y metodológicamente ha seguido los lineamientos del flujo de revisión sistemática de la literatura científica, haciendo uso del método prisma, tabla de revisión de artículos, tabla de resúmenes, gráficos estadísticos de la literatura científica revisada, análisis de los resultados, discusión y conclusiones de la literatura revisada. Los resultados de los 23 artículos seleccionados visibilizan la postura de diferentes articulistas respecto a la comunicación del docente universitario, a la educación virtual, al vínculo entre ambos criterios y a ciertas características; la literatura refleja carencia de artículos que delimiten el impacto de las estrategias comunicativas empleadas en el proceso de educación virtual. No obstante, se encontró información relevante respecto a la importancia de la comunicación y de las habilidades comunicativas del docente en su práctica educativa y en el proceso de formación de futuros profesionales.

Palabras claves: comunicación, educación virtual, docente universitario.

As a result of the pandemic, the teaching-learning processes and their characteristics changed radically, because from a face-to-face methodology, characterized by the continuous and dynamic interaction between the teacher and the student, it was transited to a virtual methodology, which does not necessarily guarantee the presence of the student, an environment favorable, nor the acquisition of the necessary competences for their performance. These changes occurred throughout the education system; at the university level was no exception, teachers were forced to implement strategies and resources to enhance the transmission and exchange of information with students, having to reformulate their tasks and tasks to fulfill their role in the training of future professionals^{1,2}

UNESCO establishes that to guarantee the quality and continuity of virtual teaching-learning processes, the acquisition of progressive skills by those involved is necessary; To this end, it defined actions and strategies that teachers must implement in the incorporation of technological and communication aids within their educational practice. In America and the Caribbean, ECLAC (UN), defines actions for the continuous improvement and development of SDG 4 of the 2030 Agenda, establishing the need to guarantee quality and access, suggests review and reformulation of curricula and evaluation systems, as well as increase and strengthen training for educators. In 2021, the statistics show that only a third of the world's students accessed virtual education and with respect to teachers, they did not access the training, generating negative repercussions on their work and personal performance^{3,4}

In our country, Law 30220, in its article 6° guarantees access, increase and transmission of science, technology, culture and artistic manifestations, as well as the integral training of young people and adults capable of exercising their profession with high responsibility and critical sense, who respond to the current demands of our society, capable of promoting research and work in favor of the community; In its article 47, it delimits distance education making use of virtuality as a possibility and strategy⁵. In the context of health in 2020, Legislative Decree 1496 was approved, which implements the rules to give continuity to blended higher education and distance education; promoting in the latter, the interaction between the actors of the teaching-learning process (synchronous or asynchronous), making use of technology for the development of the educational act⁶.

In 2020, UNESCO, in coordination with the Ministry of Education of Peru, implemented strategies to strengthen education in the context of virtuality, making visible the need to enhance the skills and capacities of educators for the creation and use of resources that allow them to have tools for the development of the respective themes and knowledge. The importance of the teacher and the need to develop skills that guarantee quality educational processes were valued; The trainings were focused on the development of social, emotional, management, design and implementation skills for virtual education, as well as to enhance empathy and resilience in educators⁷.

In 2021, office of the ombudsman its report N°005-2021-DP/AMASPP, states that INEI figures reflect a decrease in participation in the virtual educational process and that the state, trying to address part of the problem, approved a budget item for higher education students in extreme poverty, aimed at acquiring internet service⁸. However, these attempts have not been enough to improve the quality of virtual education. In this same context of negative impact of virtuality, it is known of the existence of emotional and physical difficulties as a result of the virtual educational process⁹; In this sense, an introspective analysis of the educational act, its factors and internal components that limit or facilitate the acquisition of skills and competencies for professional development and exercise is necessary; this is where, among many other skills of the teacher to implement their virtual educational practice, the communication strategies used and their impact become relevant. in the training of future professionals.

Therefore, communication is fundamental within the process of academic training, it is considered that every professional requires the use of the word as a tool for their performance, so the possibility of having strategies and communication skills favors a better development and significant achievements in the professional work; it is therefore essential to develop these skills from the process of professional training, having greater relevance in those who fall the responsibility of training competent people capable of responding adequately to the needs of today's society and of generating the necessary transformations¹⁰⁻¹².

Among the criteria of communication, speech is considered as the possibility of connecting through the spoken word and listening as the possibility of taking attention, understanding and being empathetic with what the person transmits orally, in both cases the educational actors must work on developing and enhancing them. In communication there are characteristics to be considered during any educational act: volume, speed, intonation, clear, coherent and complete premises^{10,13}.

Faced with what has been described, it is evident that to develop teaching and research, educators need to link and interact with their students, for this communication skills become fundamental, thus, we can cite the collaborative learning model, with the triad educator, content and students, which values interaction and communication, dependence between actors and the development of social competences, as some attributes for the success of the model; in this sense, the curricular structuring in higher education must consider contents and values that allow teamwork, self-management, oral, written, digital communication, etc. Consequently, it is crucial to promote a communicative culture, based on dialogue, that improves and makes pleasant moments of interaction and learning, that enhances spaces of peace through critical and sensible resolution of conflicts, that promotes broad, varied, critical and analytical intellectual activity, to assume responsible positions and attitudes^{8,10,12,13}.

Considering that the world is currently digitized, and that this digitalization has significant repercussions on educational processes; today we speak of virtual education, referring to

education that creates and conditions areas of permanent interrelation between educational actors, valuing temporality, space, use of technology, connectivity, knowledge and management of virtual tools and instruments, which meets the need to implement new strategies, pedagogical and didactic methodologies, in which a favorable attitude of the teacher is required in front of the virtuality that allows him to enhance the educational experience¹⁴⁻¹⁸.

Within this framework, for virtual education, the digital classroom is considered as the space where the academic experience and the interaction between the teacher and the student occurs, based on specific contents to develop competencies in students; the virtual community considers all the agents that participate in this virtual event online; connectivity refers to the connection to the internet service that allows and the transmission and reception of information, favoring participation in the virtual educational event; The technological infrastructure considers the equipment and/or physical and logical supports that are required to execute specific activities; it is also called software and hardware; educational software are the programs that enable participation in the virtual educational act and hardware are the physical equipment that allows access, connection and participation in virtual learning sessions^{18,19}.

For a better understanding, it is noteworthy that there is evidence of asynchronous and synchronous virtual educational modalities, blended and virtual is, which visualizes the need for technological infrastructure for teaching-learning processes, but there is also the need to develop personal skills of the educator that allow him to direct the educational process with relevance, implementing resources and methodological strategies for the acquisition of competences; Thus, institutions need to adapt their modalities, processes and contents, develop resources and skills according to these new educational characteristics. It is important to note that virtuality has had a negative impact on some actors in the educational community, having important repercussions, such as economic deficit, unemployment, health alterations, time incompatibility, among others, that hinder participation in the virtual educational experience; however, the teacher must have skills and support to overcome and being resilient, become the mediator that will enable learning experiences valuing the characteristics of students and their contexts, demonstrating commitment to them^{1,21-24}.

In response to the aforementioned considerations, communication immersed in virtual education, requires different educational links, paradigm shift, curricular redesigns and development of competencies that guarantee comprehensive and quality professional training; this educational modality has been welcomed in a sector of the population, so the need to make it more flexible and promote its continuity is visualized, considering the necessary changes and the empowerment of competencies in teachers and students; Thus, educators have a challenge, in which the need to communicate predominates, implements content, resources and strategies that allow access to the student; This is why teachers need and commit to propose, modify and develop social, emotional, digital and communicative competencies for their performance in virtual classrooms²⁵⁻³¹.

Methodology

Regarding the methodological aspect, the article has followed the guidelines of the flow of systematic review of the scientific literature, making use of the prism method, review table of articles, table of abstracts, statistical graphs of the reviewed scientific literature, analysis of the results, discussion and conclusions of the reviewed literature.

The objective was to describe the importance of university teacher communication in the teaching-learning process within virtual educational practice.

For the review process, searches were carried out at various times in the databases of Scielo, Dialnet, Scopus, Latindex, Redalyc, having among the search criteria "communication of university teachers", "importance of teaching communication in virtuality", "teaching communication strategies", "communication skills in teachers", "virtual education", "role of the teacher in virtual education". The filters used for these searches were: by type of literature, scientific articles; period 2016 – 2021; S languages Spanish, English and Portuguese.

For the selection process, inclusion and exclusion criteria were considered; originality of the articles was delimited for inclusion, publication in scientific journals, with indexing in databases during the period 2016 – 2021, linked to importance, strategies and communication skills of the teachers, virtual education and the relationship between the two; For the exclusion, the information was filtered according to type of literature (theses and books were excluded), due to its duplicity in the databases, due to its lack of downloadable format and inconsistency in the abstracts of the selected material.

Results

For the preparation of this article, the search for several articles was carried out during the period of July 2021 - December 2021, locating 62 articles of interest; according to the selected databases, Scielo (24), Dialnet (19), Redalyc (15) and Scopus 4 were found. Once the selection was made, we proceeded to filter according to the characteristics of the information, the first filter was to discard articles for duplicity, obtaining 21 excluded articles; The second filter was to discard due to inconsistency with the subject of study, excluding 18 articles. Finally, there were 23 articles of interest selected for the topic of study. Figure 1 graphically outlines the filtering process of the articles.

Figure 1

Item selection flowchart.

The systematic review and analysis of the 23 selected articles was carried out, as follows:

Regarding the database to which they belong, there are 15 articles from Scielo, 5 articles from Redalyc and 3 articles from Dialnet, whose equivalence in percentage is 65.22%, 21.74% and 13.04% respectively. In relation to the approach developed in the selected articles, 6 articles correspond to a quantitative approach, 12 articles to the qualitative approach and 5 are mixed approach. Considering the years of publication of the articles in reference, we found 1 article published in 2016, 4 in 2018, 1 in 2019, 9 in 2020 and 8 in 2021, the percentages of this information can be graphically visualized in figure 2.

According to the origin of the selected articles and grouping them according to the continent, 3 articles belong to Europe and 20 articles belong to America, of the latter, 7 are from South America and 13 from North America. Additionally, the amount is mentioned according to countries of origin: Cuba (8), Chile (2), Bolivia (1), Ecuador (1), Spain (3), Mexico (5), Peru (2) and Uruguay (1).

As part of the systematic review and analysis of the 23 articles selected for the study, Table 1 was developed, with the relationship and information regarding titles, authors, countries, study focus, year, database, and journals to which they belong.

Figure 2

Graph of selected systematic review articles according to year of publication.

Table 1. Bibliometric table of selected systematic review articles.

DATABASE	YEAR	MAGAZINE	TITLE	AUTHOR(S)	COUNTRY	STUDY APPROACH	LANGUAGE
Scielo	2021	Exchanges	Didactic-pedagogical strategies in emergency educational contexts.	Angeriz, Esther De León, Darío Chiarino, Nicholas Cuevasanta, Diego	Uruguay	Qualitative	Spanish
Scielo	2021	Interdisciplinary	Messages issued by university professors to their students with low academic performance during online teaching due to COVID-19	Lobo, Karla; Saéz-Delgado, Fabiola; López-Angulo, Yaranay; Arancibia, Susana; Maldonado, Alejandra	Chile	Qualitative	Spanish
Scielo	2021	Contemporary dilemmas	Social representations of teaching competencies in virtual learning environments in times of pandemic.	Garay, Jesus	Mexico	Qualitative	Spanish
Scielo	2021	Nova scientia	Personal motivation and self-management of learning in students, as a result of the transition to online courses during the COVID-19 pandemic	Chavez, Thomas Benitez, Adriana Alcantara, Manuel Vergara, Arely Ogando, Ana	Mexico	Mixed	English
Scielo	2021	Mexican Journal of Educational Research	Factors of satisfaction of students in e-learning in Colombia.	Segovia, Nuria Said, Elias	Mexico	Quantitative	Spanish
Scielo	2021	Conrad	Pedagogical communication as an innovation in the teaching-learning of law.	Zhinin, John Machado, Messiah Viteri, Beatriz	Cuba	Qualitative	Spanish
Scielo	2021	Communication	Happiness in times of pandemic and virtual education: a study in university students of the Altiplano	Vargas, Kleiber Callata, Zaida	Peru	Quantitative	Spanish
Scielo	2020	RIDE	Implications of the coronavirus covid-19 on teaching processes in higher education.	Gazca, Luis	Cuba	Quantitative	Spanish
Scielo	2020	Conrad	Virtuality in Education. Key aspects for the continuity of teaching in times of pandemic	Juanes, Blas Munévar, Omar Cándelo, Henry	Cuba	Qualitative	Spanish
Scielo	2020	Higher Medical Education,	Distance medical education in times of COVID-19.	Vergara, Esteban Vergara, Rodrigo Álvarez, Mayita Camacho, Luis Gálvez, José	Peru	Qualitative	Spanish
Scielo	2020	Higher education	The construction of educational interpersonal communication, mediated by social networks and educational platforms, in the careers of Education Sciences and Psychology, of the Universidad Mayor de San Andrés	Ordoñez, Klondy	Bolivia	Mixed	Spanish
Scielo	2020	Higher Medical Education	Didactic strategies for the virtualization of the teaching-learning process in times of COVID-19.	Vialart, Maria	Cuba	Qualitative	Spanish
Scielo	2020	RIDE. Rev. Iberoam. Investigate. Development. Educ	Design of a blended learning environment as a proposal for educational innovation at the University of Sierra Juárez.	Mendez, Florentino Morales, Magda	Mexico	Qualitative	Spanish
Scielo	2019	Cuban Journal of Higher Education	Identification and practice of values in university education.	Kings, Olga Hernandez, Gladys	Cuba	Quantitative	Spanish
Scielo	2018	Conrad	Cooperative teaching-learning processes applied by university teachers	Mendez, Edgar Mina, Alexandra Mendez, Hyacinth	Cuba	Mixed	Spanish
Redalyc	2020	Ibero-American Journal of Educational Studies	Higher education in times of pandemic: a view from within the training process.	Michael, Joseph	Mexico	Mixed	Spanish
Redalyc	2018	Athens	Interactive virtual education, the paradigm of the future.	Perez, Carmen Suarez, Rogelio Rosillo, Nancy	Cuba	Qualitative	Spanish
Redalyc	2018	Athens	Development of communicative competence in initial teacher training	Scissors, Amparo Monsalve, Laura	Cuba	Qualitative	Spanish
Redalyc	2018	Infad: psychological journal	Analysis of teacher communication skills and action guidelines. Attracting attention by talking: A challenge for university education.	Neighborhood, Jose Neighborhood, Angela	Spain	Quantitative	Spanish
Redalyc	2016	Interuniversity Journal of Teacher Training	The role of the teacher in the digital age Magazine	Viñals, Ana Cuenca, Jaime	Spain	Qualitative	Spanish
Dialnet	2021	Publishing Magazine	Socio-Pedagogical Strategies for Virtual Education in the Framework of the Covid-19 Pandemic in Ecuador.	Perazzo, Daniel Jimenez, Ledys Heras, Jessenia	Ecuador	Qualitative	Spanish
Dialnet	2020	Latin Journal of Social Communication.	Education in times of pandemic reflections of students and teachers on university virtual education in Spain, Italy and Ecuador.	Weaver, Santiago Cervi, Laura Tusa, Fernanda Parola, Alberto	Spain	Quantitative	Spanish
Dialnet	2020	Inclusiones Magazine	Assertive communication and its impact on learning in high school students from a rights-based approach.	Lozada, Rosario Figueroa, Marilyn Plúas, Rita Ron, Maria	Chile	Mixed	Spanish

Of the 23 articles selected, it can be mentioned that 9 were linked to communication, 8 were related to casually, virtual education and 6 registered a link between both criteria considered for the systematic review.

Discussion and Conclusions

About communication Barrio & Barrio, Tijeras & Monsalve, Lobos Peña et al, Méndez et al. and Lozada et al. They agreed to link communication with people's abilities to deliver content or message, mention words and speech as a tool for professional performance, and refer to some characteristics of them (8–11, 22). For its part, Reyes & Hernández reinforce that communication is fundamental in the teaching-learning process, since, among other aspects, it allows to strengthen the formation in values, initiated at home, consolidated in schooling and consolidated in the university stage, according to the desired profile; To this end, higher education must implement strategies that guarantee competent professionals who meet current demands with ethics and relevance (32); in coincidence, Chávez et al., Zhinín et al. and Ordoñez, consider communication as the potential strategy to achieve the objectives within the educational field, for this reason the teacher assumes a leading role in the fulfillment of this task (14–16).

For virtual education, the contributions of Viñals & Cuenca, Pérez et al., Gazca, and Vergara et al. were analyzed. Those who conceptualized, described some characteristics and emphasized their impact (16 - 19); In addition, Garay, Méndez & Morales, Vargas & Callata and Perazzo et al. captured the conditions for its development, the necessary individual skills, methodologies, strategies and some repercussions on its use and implementation (1, 20 - 22).

Among the references that linked both topics, Ordoñez, Angeriz et al., Juanes et al., Vialart, Tejedor et al., Miguel and Segovia & Said were found, (27)(29)(31) who emphasized the need to create different educational links, change preconceived ideas, modify strategies and contents, as well as develop personal skills that allow to enhance learning and the gain of skills in students that guarantee quality and educational success, according to the acquisition of competences for the required profile; they proposed that all changes and/or adjustments should be adjusted to the context of virtual education in which we find ourselves and that could remain at the university level (16, 25–30).

The review of the selected articles presents a relative vision regarding the importance of teacher communication in virtual education, many agree on the importance and impact of communication in the educational process and act, however, there is a lack of deep analysis on the subject linked to virtuality, as well as techniques and communicative characteristics of the university professor in this same context.

It stands out and coincides with the writers regarding the challenge of teachers to implement communicative techniques and strategies that allow the development of the teaching-learning process under the virtual modality, generating or

adapting strategies making use of virtuality resources and promoting a different pedagogical practice. It is shared regarding the importance of distance communication, considered as a fundamental and transversal axis, which together with the implementation and proper use of technological resources can make effective and guarantee the quality of the educational process; It is of impact that for this to happen, in addition to imparting knowledge through new forms, the student must properly manage them (25–30).

On the other hand, in agreement with the writer who mentions about achieving a "culture of pedagogical communication", it is considered opportune to develop a new perspective of virtual pedagogical communication, where the teacher develops strategies that generate symmetrical, relevant and effective spaces for interaction with students, to guarantee the quality and impact of higher educational training (15).

At the university level, communication skills and their implementation become relevant, because being young adults it is necessary to assess strategies and resources that allow teachers to reformulate their tasks and tasks to fulfill their role in the training of future professionals, enhancing the transmission and exchange of information with students; That is why, in agreement with Reyes & Hernández, it is considered that teachers should implement educational strategies that promote dynamism, participation, inclusion, dialogue and meaningful learning, which allow regulating actions, the critical construction of solutions and the practice of values necessary in the training process (31).

It is concluded, after the review of the writers, that communication is a fundamental tool to carry out different activities that involve interactions between two or more people, the teaching-learning process in different educational environments is no exception. In the context of virtuality and environments different from that of conventional university educational practice, the development and use of communication skills becomes more interesting and relevant, since it is necessary to ensure that behind screens and monitors, in a physical educational space that the teacher cannot access, students receive and understand the message, knowledge, as well as the development of skills that allow you to achieve the necessary skills to perform with responsibility, ethics and professionalism.

Finally, under the gaze and need for a new pedagogy, which must be implemented by the teacher in university educational practice, virtual education becomes the possibility of reducing gaps and enhancing the teaching-learning process and it is the communicative ability that will allow access to knowledge, to awaken interest in it, to promote its use and implementation, as well as to promote the protagonist of the student and favor the approach between the protagonists of the educational act, seeking to enhance the student's performance and guarantee the achievement of the expected competences according to their study profile and the demands of today's society.

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